

NEW METHODS OF TEACHING MATHEMATICS TO MODERN LYCEUM STUDENTS

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Annotation

I imagine education at lyceum as a process of continuous, purposeful, pedagogically organized intellectual, spiritual and physical development and self-development of a person. The dominant factor in this process is the continuous development of personality. The main constituent elements of education are three qualities of the educational process: learning, as a process of transferring experience; education, as an essential component of the socialization of the individual; education, as a process of broad introduction of a person to culture.

Key words: *calculations, logical and imaginative thinking, method of differentiated learning, research activities*

In the education system, a significant change has occurred in the main link – in the content of education. This naturally led to the need for changes in the methods and forms of organization of the learning process. Modernization of the educational content has increased the level of scientific learning and led to a more effective overall development of students. The teaching process is an art, the art of captivating children with their subject, surprising them with the beauty of thought, knowledge, and encouraging independent actions. Teaching mathematics in lyceum, I believe, should be aimed at the intellectual development and self-development of students, the development of logical and imaginative thinking, characteristic of mathematical activity and necessary for a comfortable and confident life in modern society; mastering specific mathematical knowledge necessary for the study of related disciplines, for practical activities, for use in future professional activities, for successful further education in universities, continuing education and self-education. In general, this is the preparation of a graduate who is self-sufficient, sociable and competent, able to adapt to changing living conditions and the demands of modernity. Students who are mainly interested in further education come to the senior level of education, so it is interesting to work in these classes. The training takes place in an activity mode. There is mutual understanding between the teacher and the students, a common goal-setting, which is aimed at a joint positive result in work. The groups in which

I work study mathematics at a basic level, so one of the problems in teaching mathematics is the unstable interest of students in this subject, some lack the desire to learn, which entails the unwillingness to always do homework. To solve this problem, I use the method of differentiated learning. Academic lyceum education should be designed so that graduates can independently set and achieve serious goals, skillfully respond to different life situations. Teaching mathematics at lyceum should have as its main goal not the transfer of a certain amount of knowledge, but the development of the ability to obtain mathematical knowledge, taking into account the individual capabilities of each student. For each student, it is necessary to individually design his "zone of immediate development".

In working with modern lyceum students, I believe the following pedagogical methods are effective:

- the technology of the activity method allows students to develop meta-subject skills and personal results (readiness and ability of students to self-development, self-determination, ability to set goals);
- the technology of critical thinking development allows students to develop mental operations and communicative qualities;
- the technology of modular learning allows you to study the material in blocks, this is helped by the lecture-practical form of teaching mathematics at lyceum;
- the use of IT in the classroom makes the lesson more dynamic, intense, bright, which makes each student work actively, promotes the development of cognitive interest, motivates all groups of students to participate in the work, forms information competence;
- the research method of teaching develops personality qualities necessary in later life.

By organizing research activities, I form students not only special research skills and abilities, but also create conditions for the formation of all groups of universal educational activities. In the field of personal universal educational activities, the organization of research activities provides excellent opportunities for the formation of a motivational basis for educational activities among senior lyceum students, for the education of cognitive interest in educational material, the student's ability to self-esteem, the education of civic formation of personality. In the field of regulatory universal educational actions, students have the opportunity to learn how to set new educational tasks, make a work plan, plan and conduct research to find the necessary information, evaluate the information received to test hypotheses, answer a problematic question. In the field of

cognitive universal educational activities, research activity provides excellent opportunities for children to develop the ability to independently identify and formulate a problem, set a cognitive goal, put forward hypotheses and justify them, search for information from various sources, present information in different forms. In addition, during the research search, the students' ability to compare, generalize, and draw conclusions develops. In the field of communicative universal educational activities, the inclusion of children in research activities ensures the development of students' ability to work in a group, the ability to listen to the interlocutor and enter into a dialogue with him, participate in collective discussion of problems, ask questions, the ability to express their thoughts in accordance with the tasks and conditions of communication. My students take part at scientific and practical conferences, where they take prizes.

In working with lyceum students, I build the educational process using the modern educational technologies listed above. In order to deepen the knowledge and develop the creative abilities of students, instill interest in the subject, I conduct individual consultations for students. I conduct individual work with children who have difficulties in mastering the curriculum and have high educational motivation. I build my work on the principle of accessibility and entertainment. I use health-saving technologies effectively in the lessons. In order to reduce the information load, anxiety, I use compression of educational material into diagrams, reference notes. To maintain the psychological climate, relieve emotional stress, I use work in groups, work in pairs of a shift staff, organize classes with frequent changes of activities, dynamic pauses, minutes of relaxation. I pay great attention to the educational aspect in my teaching activities. The purpose of my educational work is to create conditions for the development of basic personal values (psychological, physical and moral health, individual abilities), the formation of a tolerant attitude to the world, universal values. Traditionally, formal problems written in symbolic language have been the basis of the mathematics curriculum. Previously, children didn't need to understand why math works the way it does. They just had to remember that "two times two is four." I suggest that formal learning should be consistent with real life experience. I regard mathematics as a human activity, and not just as pure absolute knowledge. The new mathematics is focused on the fact that students perceive numbers as objects and can understand the meaning of actions. The tendency of teaching is not in memorization, but through the acceptance of mathematics as a concept, through the disclosure of the beauty of science. It is

important that the child learns to be aware of it through the problems of the surrounding reality. That is, the movement towards understanding formal mathematics goes through informal channels. An important element for this trend is group work. Students achieve a higher level of understanding through interaction with peers, including during role-playing games.

Project-based learning was also registered in math lessons. This format implies the organization of the educational process in the form of solving educational tasks based on the independent collection and interpretation of information, argumentation of the position and self-examination, and at the end - the presentation of the resulting intellectual product. Students independently learn to choose and develop a topic for a future project, draw up a training plan, organize groups and assign roles within them, determine project deadlines, search and find sources of information and necessary materials for the implementation of the project, and also acquire public speaking skills. The final result can be presented in the form of an illustrated report, an interactive business or role-playing game with a classroom, a conference and even an excursion. The teacher is required, first of all, to form an environment that motivates children to conduct independent research. Approximate topics for such projects can be the origin of mathematics and algebra, the history of the appearance of fractional or negative numbers, the history of famous mathematical discoveries and biographies of great scientists, and so on. I use computer testing lessons. Test control using a computer assumes the ability to identify the knowledge and ignorance of students faster and more objectively than with the traditional method. This method of organizing the educational process is convenient and easy to evaluate in a modern information processing system. This type of control allows you to check the level of knowledge, skills and abilities of a group of students in turn in a fairly short time of the lesson, when the rest of the students perform another type of work. In the following lessons, other students are tested, so that everyone has time to pass the test by the final lesson on the topic. The program enters the test results into a statement for subsequent analysis and correction of knowledge by the teacher. It is advisable to conduct training lessons in a computer classroom, in order to form strong intellectual abilities among students. As a rule, in mathematics lessons it is a simulator for solving problems of a certain type or an environment for solving constructive problems, problems for building in the course of geometry, algebra when constructing graphs of functions. In such lessons, students individually or in a group work with some a constructive environment for the purpose of practicing a skill in solving problems

or achieving some constructive goal. Integrated lessons are usually conducted in a computer classroom where students have access to computers. Using the capabilities of standard MS Office programs, they carry out a number of calculation operations that make it possible to make a quantitative analysis of any process. In such lessons, you can simulate a certain process and, having made the necessary calculations, draw certain conclusions. Such lesson is usually conducted by a subject teacher and a computer science teacher. The subject teacher sets a task, analyzes the intermediate and final results together with the student, and draws conclusions. The computer science teacher helps students to build a mathematical model of the process and perform all the necessary calculations using this model. There are many topics in the school curriculum that are useful to consider simultaneously from the point of view of several sciences, it is in such cases that integrated lessons achieve their goal.

As a conclusion I should say that mathematics throughout the history of mankind has been an integral part of human culture, the key to understanding the world around us, the basis of scientific and technological progress. Mathematical education is a benefit to which every person has the right, and it is the duty of society to provide everyone with the opportunity to exercise this right.

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